

Polarized intensity (mJy beam⁻¹)
0.145 0.150 0.155

55°27'30"

26 z_{sp} = 0.3566

00"

26'30"

00"

25'30"

00"

100 kpc

16^h09^m45^s40^s

35^s

30^s

RA (J2000)

Dec (J2000)

